

2,2-Dimethylcyclopentanone

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In connection with another project, large quantities of pure 2,2-dimethylcyclopentanone¹ were needed in these laboratories. A satisfactory method was developed through methylation of 2-methylcyclohexanone in presence of potassium butoxide¹. It gave a mixture which was chemically separated through the hydroxymethylene derivative², leading to pure 2,2-dimethylcyclohexanone in 55% yield. Use of sodamide in place of butoxide³ gave a poorer yield (40%) in our hands³. Oxidation with nitric acid and subsequent cyclisation gave pure 2,2-dimethylcyclopentanone in 35% overall yield.

2,2-Dimethylcyclohexanone.—To a slurry of potassium salt of 2-methylcyclohexanone, prepared from 2-methylcyclohexanone (56 g.), potassium (18.5 g.), and butanol¹ (400 ml), was slowly introduced methyl iodide (78 g.) with stirring and cooling in an ice-bath. The mixture was allowed to stand at 0°—5° for 3 hrs. and then refluxed for 2 hrs. The solvent was distilled and water (300 ml) added to the residue. The organic material was taken up in benzene, repeatedly shaken with saturated sodium bisulphite solution, washed with water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed, leaving a light yellow residue.

A solution of the above residue in ethyl formate (55 g.) was added to an ice-cooled suspension of sodium methoxide (54 g.) in dry benzene (500 ml) during a period of 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight and decomposed with ice. The benzene layer was extracted with 5% NaOH solution. The aqueous layer was combined with the alkaline extract, washed with ether, and acidified with ice-cold HCl. The resulting oily suspension was taken in ether. The solvent was removed and the residue was again dissolved in 7% NaOH solution (1600 ml). The alkaline solution was slowly distilled to collect in 4 hrs. 500 ml of the distillate. This was extracted with ether and dried. The residue after removal of the solvent was fractionated to collect (35 g., 55%) colorless 2,2-dimethylcyclohexanone, b.p. 169-71°. The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 125-26° (lit.⁴ m.p. 125-26°). The semicarbazone crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 196-98° (decomp.); lit.⁴ m.p. 198.6-199.8°.

1,1-Dimethyladipic Acid.—To boiling HNO₃ (conc., 150 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring 2,2-dimethylcyclohexanone (25 g.) during 1½ hrs. The reaction mixture was concentrated over a water bath to a semisolid. The solid acid, m.p. 86-88°, was obtained by triturating the product with small quantities of water at a time. Total yield amounted to 30 g. (85%).

1. Haller and Cornubert, *Compt. rend.*, 1924, 179, 315; Bartlett and Bayley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2416; Kazanki *et al.*, *Bull. Acad. Sci., U.S.S.R., Classe Sci. Chim.*, 1947, 29; Schinz and Seifert, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, 34, 728.
2. Bailey and Madoff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2707.
3. Barnes and Houlihan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1809.
4. Johnson and Posvic, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1361.

2,2-Dimethylcyclopentanone.—A mixture of 1,1-dimethyladipic acid (10 g.) and barium hydroxide (1.5 g.) was heated at 270-90° for 3 hrs. The distillate was extracted with ether and washed with sodium carbonate solution and water. It was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation yielded 4.9 g (75%) of 2,2-dimethylcyclopentanone, b.p. 142-44°, n_D^{20} 1.4314. The *2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 140-41° (Haller and Cornubert¹ report m.p. 141-41.5°). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 190-91° (Bartlett and Bavley² report m.p. 191.5-91.8°). There was no depression of mixed m.p. with derivatives of 2,2-dimethylcyclopentanone prepared by direct methylation.

After the completion of this work a similar method (17% overall yield) has been reported by Wilcox and Mesirov.³

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